

Deliverable D4.3

Provenance model for infectious diseases

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1. Executive Summary

The exchange of research objects, such as specimens and research data, is common for modern research. However, several reports¹²³⁴⁵ indicated issues with reproducibility and quality of the exchanged research objects. Poor documentation quality of processes related to specimen and data generation are stated as one of the most common causes.

Additionally, significant impact of flawed research results on economics, health, and political decisions is stated, as we could also witness during the COVID-19 pandemic⁶. In order to prevent these issues, professional societies and research initiatives call for improved and standardised documentation of the data and specimens used in research studies.

Provenance is information about the history of a documented object – be it physical or digital. In particular, provenance captures information about entities, activities, or agents that were involved in or affected the creation of the object. Depending on particular information included in provenance, it can be used for various purposes, including traceability of precursors of documented objects. For instance, given a result of a data analysis, provenance can be used to trace the input data used for the analysis, the original data sources, the methods used to generate the data, or the sources for data generation, such as biological material from which the data was generated (e.g., omics data, image data). This way, provenance information can heavily contribute to the reproducibility of the results, ability to assess their quality or fitness-for-purpose, auditability, or other purposes.

This deliverable describes a general provenance information model for infectious diseases. The underlying provenance model is designed to support distributed multi-organizational provenance information, which is generated when a documented object's life cycle spans multiple organisations, such as a sample acquired in a hospital, data generated from the sample in a laboratory, and the data processed and analysed by a research group by a university or a private company. The provenance model supports traceability of precursors of a documented object (e.g., a dataset) by providing the data derivation chain back to original sources of the data, such as biological samples from which data was generated. The model supports FAIRness (especially Reusability) of a documented object by providing standardised means to attach to or link relevant information from provenance. The provenance model enables parts of provenance traces to be kept confidential or anonymised to preserve confidentiality and privacy of respective personal data subjects, such as patients, donors, or responsible people.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.114.303819>

² <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0063221>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.114.303819>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.03981>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1177/1177271919829162>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.368.6495.1041>

The deliverable also describes a set of RO-Crate⁷ [Soiland-Reyes 2022a] profiles to capture the provenance of the execution of computational workflows, with different levels of granularity. The RO-Crate format enables the description and packaging of the available artefacts and their metadata into a lightweight de-facto-standardised format.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal .	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	Yes
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	Yes
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	Yes

⁷ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

	<p>3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.</p> <p>4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p> <p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p> <p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral Data Hubs across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p> <p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>

<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p>	No
	<p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	Yes

3. Methods

The work towards the development of a provenance model tailored for infectious diseases started with a gap analysis regarding the current state of the art for distributed provenance information, the Common Provenance Model (CPM, a conceptual foundation for the ISO 23494 series). The analysis uncovered a gap in the specification of a mechanism for linking provenance information and its meta-data (meta-provenance). As a result, requirements on linking provenance and its meta-data in distributed multi-organizational environments were formulated. As the provenance model was initially developed in the EOSC-Life project⁸, the emerging requirements were provided back to the EOSC-Life where they were addressed (extending the model to support the linking mechanism). Once the requirements were addressed and the model refined in the EOSC-Life, the development of the model continued within the BY-COVID project by simplifying the model, by specification of supported operations for distributed provenance, and by adoption of the model for selected BY-COVID use cases.

The actual adoption of the CPM in the BY-COVID project was initiated by organising a provenance workshop, where workshop participants coming from various work packages (WPs) of the project worked out a questionnaire regarding the information needed to design and create provenance information according to the model. After the workshop, WP4 in cooperation with other WPs iteratively refined the initial provenance design to incorporate more granular provenance descriptions into the resulting provenance, and refined the provenance model in parallel.

The development of the Workflow Run Crate profiles emerged in the EOSC-Life project, and was accelerated by BY-COVID for the purpose of tracking computational workflow executions, particularly in established workflow engines CWL and Galaxy, but also a need was identified in the BY-COVID use cases to support manual or semi-manual “workflows” such as using computational notebooks interactively.

RO-Crate is a general set of practices for publishing FAIR data packaging. The RO-Crate community had been established around the idea of using Linked Data standards in a pragmatic way, specifying patterns by examples and the schema.org vocabulary. In EOSC-Life, a profile for Workflow RO-Crate⁹ had been developed by the early COVID-19 WorkflowHub¹⁰, capturing the FAIR metadata for computational workflows and their requirements.

⁸ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

⁹ <https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/>

¹⁰ <http://covid19.workflowhub.eu/>

A open working group¹¹ for Workflow Run Crate was started within the RO-Crate community, as of 2024-03-05 the group has 35 members. The group meets bi-weekly in Zoom calls with asynchronous Slack messages. In addition to BY-COVID partners from WP4, the group engages multiple members from ELIXIR Europe and other EOSC projects.

Early on, the group started requirements gathering, and organised these into a series of competency questions¹². These were then expanded as GitHub issues, where solutions based on existing schema.org terms were drafted and formalised into a set of profile specifications for workflow provenance (see [section 4.2](#)). This work, driven largely by BY-COVID partners, also informed the RO-Crate community on how its profiles should be specified¹³.

The development of the provenance model and the framework for FAIR digital objects were piloted on various use cases coming from the project. In particular:

- **Interaction with the WP1** “Support for virological analyses in emerging disease outbreaks”
 - The resulting provenance model was applied to the data deposition process in a data hub, which is part of the WP1.
- **Interaction with the WP2** “Accessing heterogeneous data across domains and jurisdictions for enabling the downstream processing of COVID-19 and future pandemic episodes data”
 - The resulting provenance model was applied to the clinical health data transformation into the OMOP Common Data Model, which is part of the WP2.
 - Following a joint workshop, the Federated Analytics work adapted the Workflow Run RO-Crate profile to form a specialised profile for trusted research environments.
- **Interaction with WP3** “COVID-19 integration platform”
 - The COVID-19 Data Portal was adjusted to index Workflow RO-Crates from WorkflowHub
 - Collaboration with ISIDORE on use of RO-Crate [David 2023b]
- **Interaction with WP5** “A continuously evolving demonstrator project feeding the changing research questions that surface during an on-going pandemic to solutions.”
 - The resulting provenance model was applied to the selected demonstrators of the WP5 (the baseline use case (T5.2), the clinical trials use case (T5.3)).
 - The baseline use case pipeline was documented as a Workflow Run RO-Crate and registered in WorkflowHub.

¹¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/#community>

¹² <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/requirements>

¹³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.2-DRAFT/profiles>

- **Interaction with WP6** “Engage, train and build capacity with national and international stakeholders”
 - Development of detailed online training material for Workflow RO-Crate at Galaxy Smörgåsbord 2023
 - Several training events for RO-Crate including for ELIXIR All Hands, FAIR Digital Object Summit 2024

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Common Provenance Model

The Common Provenance Model (CPM) is a W3C PROV¹⁴-based general provenance model for describing the processing of biological material, data generation, and computational workflows. The model serves as a generic horizontal framework designated for adoption in various domains of life sciences. The model is intended for distributed environments, where multiple organisations are involved in processing of an object, such as a sample or data that are exchanged between the organisations – a sender and a receiver. In such scenarios, each of the organisations involved in the object processing generates provenance information documenting part of the object’s life cycle and interconnects the generated provenance bundle with bundles generated by other organisations, which leads into creation of *provenance chains*. In addition, each component of a provenance chain has related meta-data (so called meta-provenance or provenance-of-provenance) that includes, for instance, versioning information about a particular provenance component or its hash/digital signature. A schema of a provenance chain is depicted in Figure 4.1.1.

Figure 1. Schema of a multi-organizational provenance chain.

¹⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

The resulting provenance chains provide direct support for the traceability of precursors of documented objects, and provide groundwork for other purposes, such as reproducibility of documented processes, or quality (fitness-for-purpose) assessment of documented objects.

Considering the heterogeneity of organisations across infectious diseases-related scientific, medical, public health and policy domains, and the fact that related objects are commonly shared in this environment (including biological material or data), the CPM has a strong potential to support traceability, reproducibility, and FAIRness of the exchanged objects. The heterogeneity is exemplified, for instance, in the Baseline use case of the BY-COVID project (WP5, T5.2), where a standardised workflow for population health research was developed. A research question on vaccine effectiveness (i.e., the effectiveness of primary vaccination in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection) in different regions or countries in Europe was assessed, and its assessment required the integration of heterogeneous data sources. The evaluation just for Belgium required data integration from 5 different sources, each dataset having a different origin.

Depending on the actual content of the resulting provenance, having a standardised documentation of the origins provides groundwork for automated and rapid evaluation of the results. In particular, the standardised provenance information can be queried or processed by common tools that rely on the standardised provenance representation, which can consequently support rapid responses to new infectious disease outbreaks.

The BY-COVID project has adopted the provenance model and significantly contributed to its development. In particular, the following contributions related to the provenance model were carried out as part of the BY-COVID project.

1. The core of the model – *provenance backbone* – was simplified.
2. A categorization of approaches for exchanging documented research objects and their provenance was created. Based on the categorization, requirements on linking provenance and meta-provenance were formulated. These requirements were later fed back to the EOSC-Life project, where a mechanism for linking provenance and meta-provenance for distributed multi-organisational environments was developed.
3. A specification of operations for adding new components into a provenance chain was defined. The specification includes the new mechanism for linking provenance and meta-provenance.
4. A face-to-face provenance workshop was organised to kick-off the interaction with the other WPs with the aim to adopt the provenance model.
5. The resulting provenance model was used to generate provenance for selected use cases from the BY-COVID project.

4.1.1 Simplification of the provenance backbone

Provenance information generated according to the CPM consists of two parts: 1) traversal information that is used for navigation and traversal of provenance chains; 2) domain specific provenance that provides details of the processes carried out and documented by provenance. This is depicted in Figure 4.1.2.

Figure 2. Simplified schema of a provenance chain consisting of three provenance components.

The information in each component is expressed according to the CPM as an annotated graph, where nodes of the graph represent *entities*, *activities*, or *agents* involved in producing a documented object, and edges of the graph represent their mutual *relations*. Nodes and edges are referred to as *provenance structures*. The annotations of nodes and edges specify further domain/scenario specific information, such as types of nodes or edges. As part of the BY-COVID project, the graph representation of the traversal information was simplified – two types of the graph nodes were removed from the specification, as they showed up unnecessary making the adoption of the model more difficult. Consequently, the structure of the traversal information was revised.

The new simplified version of the traversal information is presented in Appendix I.

4.1.2 Provenance Exchange Schemes and Requirements on Linking Provenance and Meta-provenance

As part of the model development, it was necessary to define how to create standardised links between components of a provenance chain and their corresponding metadata (*meta-provenance*). However, the available work on provenance lacked a thorough assessment of how potential linking mechanisms, characteristics of exchanged objects, and related requirements affect each other. For that reason, a novel categorization of potential approaches for exchanging provenance between organisations, meta-information, as well as descriptions of their respective properties was carried out as part of the BY-COVID

project. Based on this categorization, the requirements on links between the components of a distributed provenance chain and their meta-provenance were formulated.

The categorization and derived requirements on provenance and meta-provenance linking are available in sections 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3 of a preprint¹⁵.

The resulting requirements were provided to the EOSC-Life project, where the development of the links was carried out. The links are realised using persistent identifiers, which are globally unique, persistent, and resolvable. These identifiers are used for the traversal information and related provenance structures, namely forward connectors, backward connectors, and main activities. The actual links are created by having graph nodes (with the same identifier) in the linked components in a way, where the node in the sender's component is of type forward connector, and the node in the receiver's component is of type backward connector. Such a persistent identifier then resolves to the following information: 1) type of the provenance structure, which is identified by given identifier; 2) depending on the type of the provenance structure, the identifier of provenance component, in which the entity is included; 3) identifier of meta-provenance component that documents the referenced provenance component.

4.1.3 Description of Provenance Chain Operations

A provenance chain is formed by provenance components which can be added to the chain by two types of operations *with respect to an existing provenance component*.

- 1) Adding a consecutive component.
- 2) Adding a preceding component.

As part of the BY-COVID project, a technical specification of how provenance components can be added to a chain was created. The specification respects the new provenance components linking mechanism, and can be used as a guideline for implementations that would implement provenance information management according to the CPM.

The operations specification is provided in the Appendix II.

4.1.4 Provenance Workshop

The CPM was used in the BY-COVID project to document selected processes and outputs produced by the project. This activity contributed to the development of the provenance model, as it provided additional experience from infectious diseases related use cases, for which the model had not been adopted before.

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<https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/linking-provenance-and-its-metadata-in-multi-organizational-envir>

The initial step of the CPM adoption in the project was organising a provenance workshop, where project partners from various use cases answered a pre-prepared questionnaire (See Appendix III). The provenance workshop aimed to collect information about research objects exchanged between organisations in the BY-COVID project. The collected information from selected questionnaires was later used for designing provenance information for particular use cases/scenarios according to the CPM (ISO 23494-2). The workshop took place in Barcelona as part of the BY-COVID General Assembly, where sixteen respondents divided into groups by use cases answered the questionnaire. This activity resulted in ten filled questionnaires (in various levels of details).

4.1.5 Provenance Model for Infectious Diseases

Based on the information gathered during the provenance workshop, WP4 applied the CPM (ISO 23494-2) to various infectious diseases related use cases. The result of this activity are manually generated provenance chains that document particular research objects and related processes and demonstrate how the data derivation chain back to object's precursors can look like in infectious diseases related scenarios.

The resulting provenance components have various levels of granularity for various use cases, depending on the maturity of particular use cases. For instance, the WP1 Raw genomic data deposition in a data hub (a COVID-19 raw read dataset, which also shows in the COVID-19 Data Portal¹⁶) was mature enough to include all the available information from the underlying data hub into the generated provenance. On the other hand, the provenance for the Clinical trials sharing use case can be viewed more like a provenance template that should be instantiated with the actual metadata in future, as the underlying EU-COVAT-1-AGED¹⁷ dataset is still being collected, and no detailed information is available at the time of preparing this document.

The resulting provenance chains are described in the Appendix IV.

4.2 Workflow Run RO-Crate Profile Collection

RO-Crate is a recent approach to packaging research data together with their metadata. The approach is general enough to be able to describe any object, but can also be made as specific as needed through the use of extensions called profiles.

The Workflow Run RO-Crate Profile Collection¹⁸ (WRROC) developed as part of the project defines three RO-Crate profiles for capturing the provenance of an execution of a computational workflow with increasing granularity:

¹⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search?query=ERR11837803&requestFrom=searchBox>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-022-06791-y>

¹⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/profiles/>

- **Process Run Crate** can be used to describe the execution of one or more tools that contribute to the same computation;
- **Workflow Run Crate** is similar to Process Run Crate, but assumes that the coordinated execution of the tools is driven by a computational workflow;
- **Provenance Run Crate** extends Workflow Run Crate with guidelines for describing the internal details of each step of the workflow.

The idea of the staged level of profiles is to allow incremental details of provenance. The base profile of Process Run Crate can be recorded manually whenever a computational tool has been executed, including interactive application. The Workflow Run Crate can either be created outside of the workflow engine (e.g. the WfExS¹⁹ Workflow Execution Service [Fernandez 2023²⁰] which can run many types of workflow languages and produce such crates), or by the workflow engine itself. The most detailed Provenance Run Crate is more tightly integrated with the workflow engine as it needs to record each step's tool execution, their inputs and outputs.

Figure 3. The Workflow Run Crate profile links *prospective* and *retrospective provenance*. Reproduced from [Leo 2023a²¹]

¹⁹ <https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119457.1>

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.07852>

The profiles have been developed by several BY-COVID partners and external collaborators, building a relatively small but thriving developer community that extends beyond life sciences (e.g. climate science). Fig. 4.2.1 shows an UML class diagram for the Workflow Run Crate profile. Note the distinction between *prospective provenance* (the plan, i.e. the workflow itself) and *retrospective provenance* (what happened during the run).

Workflow engine support for WRROC, as of 2024-03-04, is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Workflow engine support for WRROC. Adapted from [Leo 2023]

Engine	Profile	Version URL/DOI	Example
cwltool ²² via runcrate ²³	Provenance	runcrate 0.5.0 ²⁴ or later	10.5281/zenodo.7774351 ²⁵
Galaxy ²⁶	Workflow	Galaxy 23.1.1 ²⁷ or later	10.5281/zenodo.7785861 ²⁸
COMPSS ²⁹	Workflow	compss 3.2 ³⁰ or later	10.5281/zenodo.7788030 ³¹
StreamFlow ³²	Provenance	Streamflow 0.2.0.dev10 ³³	10.5281/zenodo.7911906 ³⁴
WfExS ³⁵	Workflow	WfExS 0.10.1 ³⁶ or later	10.5281/zenodo.10091550 ³⁷
Sapporo ³⁸	Workflow	sapporo-service 1.5.1 ³⁹ or later	10.5281/zenodo.10134581 ⁴⁰

²² <https://github.com/common-workflow-language/cwltool>

²³ <http://www.researchobject.org/runcrate/>

²⁴ <https://github.com/ResearchObject/runcrate/releases/tag/0.5.0>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774351>

²⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/releases/tag/v23.1.1>

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785861>

²⁹ <https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/software-and-apps/software-list/comp-superscalar>

³⁰ <https://github.com/bsc-wdc/compss/releases/tag/v3.2>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788030>

³² <https://streamflow.di.unito.it/>

³³ <https://github.com/alpha-unito/streamflow/releases/tag/0.2.0.dev10>

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7911906>

³⁵ <https://wfexs-backend.readthedocs.io/>

³⁶ <https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend/releases/tag/0.10.1>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091550>

³⁸ <https://github.com/sapporo-wes/sapporo>

³⁹ <https://github.com/sapporo-wes/sapporo-service/releases/tag/1.5.1>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10134581>

Autosubmit ⁴¹	Workflow	Autosubmit v4.0.100 or later ⁴²	10.5281/zenodo.8144612 ⁴³
Nextflow ⁴⁴	Provenance	(nf-prov in development ⁴⁵)	example ⁴⁶

The preprint [Leo 2023] details the Workflow Run RO-Crate profiles, development and implementation.

4.2.1 Using Workflow Run Crate in baseline use case

The RO-Crate profile specification was adopted in the Baseline use case (WP5, T5.2). The resulting RO-Crate⁴⁷ contains: 1) a study protocol; 2) a casual data model; 3) the Common Data Model specification; 4) Synthetic data used for an analytical pipeline development; 5) the analytical pipeline.

The RO-Crate and the associated pipeline is registered in WorkflowHub as <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.502.3> – this is an example of the flexible use of the WRROC profiles, as the pipeline is implemented using Quarto Markdown, an interactive notebook format that supports multiple programming languages (in this case, R was used). WorkflowHub includes notebooks as “workflows” given that they follow reusability principles (e.g. avoid hard-coded paths). To improve reproducibility, WP5 T5.2 has also created a Docker-based container image that includes the Quarto runtime and the R dependencies required by the notebooks. A lightweight user interface has also been developed, so that the participant nodes can execute the notebook without being forced to interact with the more complex notebook interface. However, it is seen as important that users can inspect and modify the pipeline interactively as a Quarto notebook, e.g. in order to better understand statistical measures. The requirement for the expected input formats are documented both in the embedded Common Data Model as well as in the RO-Crate metadata.

The plan for federated analytics in the baseline use case is detailed in [Meurisse 2023⁴⁸] – in short the analytical pipeline is tested and calibrated with the carefully constructed public synthetic data, then the pipeline is deployed at the premises of each participant node to process their linked and transformed local sensitive data, with only the aggregate results committed across national boundaries for overall analysis.

⁴¹ <https://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/>

⁴² <https://pypi.org/project/autosubmit/4.0.100/>

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8144612>

⁴⁴ <https://nextflow.io/>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/nextflow-io/nf-prov/pull/19>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/nextflow-io/nf-prov/files/13070992/ro-crate-metadata.json>

⁴⁷ <https://w3id.org/ro/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6913045>

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>

This pipeline is therefore also a prime candidate for provenance tracking using the distributed CPM model, as the detailed provenance at each site is also sensitive and would vary with regards to data ingestion needs. CPM templates are being developed based on outcomes of the BY-COVID provenance workshop (See [appendix 11.2.3](#)).

We're next developing a template system so that each site can report an RO-Crate of their execution, published to Zenodo, referencing the general pipeline crate, and without divulging their sensitive data. This then can provide the final aggregate analytics with persistent identifiers and meta-provenance for each site's data, as well as recording the version of the baseline pipeline used.

4.2.2 Federated analytics with Five Safe Crate

Working with WP2, we arranged a BY-COVID hackathon to explore further using Workflow Run RO-Crate as part of federated analytics, but where the RO-Crate represents the workflow that is to be executed in a trusted research environment (TRE). In this approach, the crate contains initially *prospective provenance* – the plan for what should happen – which is then reviewed and approved for execution within the TRE's firewalled and sandboxed environment. The crate is then augmented with the final results and becomes a Workflow Run Crate with *retrospective provenance* – what did happen. This is an important element for transparency and data usage registers, as well as for reproducibility and platform interoperability, as the crate isolates workflow engine specifics from the general request.

The prototypes from this BY-COVID hackathon formed part of what became the UKRI/DARE UK funded TRE-FX⁴⁹ project's **Five Safe Crate**⁵⁰ [Soiland-Reyes 2023d⁵¹], which expands the Workflow Run RO-Crate profiles above to formally describe the request and review process. In this profile, the human and automated decisions are also recorded, and the crate contains sufficient information to inform such decisions and follow the Five Safes principles⁵² (Safe Data, Safe Projects, Safe People, Safe Settings, Safe Outputs).

With WP2 a BY-COVID workshop on Federated Analytics⁵³ was arranged with over 50 participants, which covered:

- DataSHIELD and EUCAN-connect
- The Galaxy platform and its distributed compute infrastructure
- Federated cohort data analysis in CINECA and options for B1MG
- The TEHDAS vision for services and architecture of the EHDS for secondary use of health data

⁴⁹ <https://trefx.uk/>

⁵⁰ <https://w3id.org/5s-crate/>

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350>

⁵² <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

⁵³ <https://www.elixir-belgium.org/events/federated-analysis-solutions-workshop>

- Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI): a federated research infrastructure for a rapid policy response
- HDR UK: Bringing federated analytics across trusted research environments. Detailing current capabilities and future ambitions
- Setting up data sensitive workflows execution environments with WfExS-backend

The approach of Five Safe Crates has now influenced two larger initiatives that aim for federated analytics and workflow execution both in UK, through Health Data Research (HDR UK)⁵⁴ which scales up the TRE-FX effort, as well as in the Horizon Europe project EOSC-ENTRUST⁵⁵ bringing together 34 partners to *create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.*

4.3 Common Provenance Model RO-Crate Profile

CPM RO-Crate Profile enables identification of CPM provenance chain components in an RO-Crate. The specification of the profile is publicly available on the profile webpage⁵⁶. An example of how the profile can be used is demonstrated in an example⁵⁷, where the profile is used to pack the artefacts related to an AI model training.

4.4 Relation to the Infectious Diseases Toolkit

The Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)⁵⁸, developed as part of the BY-COVID project (WP4 T4.1), provides best practices and solutions to data challenges that affect the response to infectious diseases outbreaks.

The provenance-related work contributed to the content of the IDTk⁵⁹ by providing general information about the best practices for provenance information, and by putting them into the context of infectious diseases (various sections of the Provenance IDTk page, such as Human Clinical and Health Data or Pathogen Characterization). In addition, the resulting provenance information (Appendix IV) will be presented as in the Showcase section of the IDTk to present the current state of the art in distributed provenance for infectious diseases.

The IDTk is still under development, and the full content will be published on the IDTk website by the end of the project.

⁵⁴ <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/research/research-data-infrastructure/federated-analytics/>

⁵⁵ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

⁵⁶ <https://by-covid.github.io/cpm-ro-crate/>

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8095888>

⁵⁸ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/provenance/>

5. Results

The work accomplished from *Section 4 “Description of work accomplished”* and related work was disseminated in multiple publications and activities:

- Lightweight Distributed Provenance Model for Complex Real-world Environments [Wittner 2022⁶⁰]
 - A research paper presenting the novel provenance model for multi-organizational environments.
- Provenance of specimen and data—A prerequisite for AI development in computational pathology [Plass 2023⁶¹]
 - A research paper presenting the importance of the model for computational pathology domain.
- Linking provenance and its metadata in multi-organizational environments (preprint) [Wittner 2023b⁶²]
 - A working paper (under revision at the time of writing) presenting the extension of the provenance model. The paper is being split into two separate papers to make the content more focused, one on the linking aspect, and the other on the use of distributed provenance. Submission of these is anticipated for April 2024.
- Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate [Leo 2023⁶³]
 - A preprint (submitted to PLOS One, 2024) presenting the Workflow Run RO-Crate set of profiles for capturing the provenance of the execution of computational workflows at different levels of granularity and bundling together all their associated products.
- Provenance workshop organised as part of the second BY-COVID project general assembly.
 - Focused on generating CPM templates for use cases. See [section 4.1.4](#) and <https://by-covid.org/events/by-covid-general-assembly-2023/>
- Workflow Run RO-Crate profiles specifications
 - Published with persistent identifiers at <https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun> and in Zenodo [WRROC 2023a⁶⁴] [WRROC 2023b⁶⁵] [WRROC 2023c⁶⁶]
- CPM RO-Crate profile specification
 - Published with persistent identifiers at <https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate>

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01537-6>

⁶¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2023.09.006>

⁶² <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/linking-provenance-and-its-metadata-in-multi-organizational-envir>

⁶³ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.07852>

⁶⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203944>

⁶⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203971>

⁶⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203978>

- “Be sustainable”: EOSC-Life recommendations for implementation of FAIR principles in life science data handling [David 2023a⁶⁷]
 - The paper developed as part of the EOSC-Life project. As the BY-COVID project significantly contributed to the provenance model development, the paper acknowledged the support of the BY-COVID project.
- Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data: lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness [David 2023b⁶⁸]
 - Joint paper by the ISIDORE⁶⁹ project for Infectious Disease Outbreak Research and BY-COVID. The article and supplementary material (<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2023-035.s1>) show how RO-Crate and CPM can be used for FAIR data sharing and provenance tracking.
- Leo, Simone “RO-Crate for workflow run provenance” talk at the CWL Conference 2023, February 2023
- Leo, Simone “RO-Crate and workflow execution provenance” talk at OSA2Micro – An Open Science Approach for Microbiology data integration, July 2023
- Making workflow provenance FAIR across workflow systems with Workflow Run RO-Crate [Leo 2023d⁷⁰]
 - Poster presented at ELIXIR All Hands
- Workflows Community Summit 2022: A Roadmap Revolution [Da Silva 2022⁷¹]
 - Workflow Run Crate was presented at this workshop that brought together many workflow engine creators and users. WRROC is proposed as a mechanism for workflow provenance.

The work on Workflow Run Crate is interlinked with that of the FAIR Digital Object⁷² (FDO) concept, which will be examined further in the EOSC project EuroScienceGateway⁷³. FDO-related dissemination includes:

- Enhancing RDM in Galaxy by integrating RO-Crate [De Geest 2022⁷⁴]
 - FDO2022 poster that presents Workflow Run Crate implementation in Galaxy
- RO-Crates Meets FAIR Digital Objects [Castro 2023⁷⁵]
 - CORDi poster that aligns RO-Crate with the FDO requirements,

⁶⁷ <https://doi.org/10.15252/emj.2023115008>

⁶⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2023-035>

⁶⁹ <https://isidore-project.eu/>

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119445.1>

⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.00019>

⁷² <https://fairdo.org/1316-2/>

⁷³ <https://eurosciencegateway.eu/>

⁷⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e95164>

⁷⁵ <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.396>

- Evaluating FAIR Digital Object and Linked Data as distributed object systems [Soiland-Reyes 2024a⁷⁶]
 - Journal article that compares FDO with Linked Data approaches using a series of frameworks.
- Updating Linked Data practices for FAIR Digital Object principles [Soiland-Reyes 2022b⁷⁷]
 - FDO2022 talk that shows BY-COVID experiences with RO-Crate and WorkflowHub as examples of doing FDO using Signposting
- Building diverse FDO Collections using RO-Crate
 - FDO 2022 talk detailing RO-Crate for aggregations
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5GYdN5B1tc8>
- Creating lightweight FAIR Digital Objects with RO-Crate [Soiland-Reyes 2022c⁷⁸]
 - FDO2022 poster that shows RO-Crate as metadata layer for FDO

Several ELIXIR Biohackathon projects continued work on RO-Crate and provenance with the wider wider life science community:

- BioHackEU22 Report: Enhancing Research Data Management in Galaxy and Data Stewardship Wizard by utilising RO-Crates [Eguinoa 2023⁷⁹]
- BioHackEU23: FAIR Workflow Execution with WfExS and Workflow Run Crate [Fernández 2023b⁸⁰]
- BioHackEU23 report: Enabling FAIR Digital Objects with RO-Crate, Signposting and Bioschemas [Soiland-Reyes 2024b⁸¹]

In addition, BY-COVID work on provenance and RO-Crate is attributed to work in other fields: biodiversity [Woolland 2022⁸²], plant genomics [Beier 2024⁸³].

Software developed to support BY-COVID provenance work includes:

- ro-crate-py⁸⁴ [De Geest 2023⁸⁵]
 - General Python library for working with RO-Crate – a pre existing library that has been enhanced during the course of the project
- runcrate⁸⁶ [Leo 2023c]
 - Python tool for working with Workflow Run RO-Crate – a new library developed to interact with Workflow Run RO-Crates

⁷⁶ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.07436>

⁷⁷ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94501>

⁷⁸ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e93937>

⁷⁹ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/24jst>

⁸⁰ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2023/blob/10-paper/10/paper/paper.md>

⁸¹ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/gmk2h>

⁸² <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94349>

⁸³ <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7y2jh>

⁸⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/rocrate/>

⁸⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10017862>

⁸⁶ <https://github.com/ResearchObject/runcrate>

- Galaxy⁸⁷
 - Implementation of workflow invocation export as Workflow Run RO-Crate

Training material developed by BY-COVID includes:

- IDTk provenance sections <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/provenance/>
- Galaxy smörgåsbord 2023 - Galaxy Training Network on *FAIR Data, Workflows, and Research*:
 - RO-Crate introduction
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-intro/tutorial.html>
 - Workflow Run RO-Crate Introduction
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-workflow-run-ro-crate/tutorial.html>
 - Exporting Workflow Run RO-Crates from Galaxy
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-in-galaxy/tutorial.html>
 - RO-Crate in Python
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-in-python/tutorial.html>
 - Best practices for workflows in GitHub repositories
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-galaxy-best-practices/tutorial.html>
 - Submitting workflows to LifeMonitor
<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-submitting-life-monitor/tutorial.html>

Work on reproducibility for FAIR Computational Workflows relates also to the BY-COVID outputs:

- Methods Included: Standardizing Computational Reuse and Portability with the Common Workflow Language [Crusoe 2023⁸⁸]
 - CWL is used as a means to achieve interoperability in BY-COVID and many other projects, but is also used as a *prospective provenance* layer in WorkflowHub, as a platform neutral description of the analysis. This formed the basis for further work in BY-COVID including the runcrate tool's support for converting CWL's CWLProv to WRROC.

⁸⁷ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/releases/tag/v23.2.1>

⁸⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1145/34868977>

6. Discussion

The adoption of the CPM in the BY-COVID project resulted in several provenance chains related to infectious diseases. Thanks to the BY-COVID project, the current state of the art provenance model is mature enough to enable full traceability of a data derivation chain back to its sources, including integrity and authenticity verification of provenance chains (relates to the meta-provenance linking). In addition, the adoption of the model for various use cases in the project demonstrates how the provenance model can be applied, providing a solid foundation for future provenance research and development in infectious diseases-related domains. Based on these two contributions, we consider the following two future directions as reasonable:

1. **Development of domain specific provenance.** The creation of the provenance chains according to the proposed model enables interoperability of distinct components of a chain providing the ability to query over them. In this context, two types of queries are distinguished. *Domain-agnostic queries* that can be run only over provenance backbone (e.g., given a dataset, what are the precursors of the dataset?), and *domain-specific queries* that require fully technically interoperable domain-specific information in a provenance component (e.g., what means were used to acquire source biological material or generate data?). In order to support domain specific queries, further research and development is required to define what exact information must be stored in the domain specific part, how it should be expressed according to the provenance model, and how it can be generated in an automated way.
2. **Extending the scope of the resulting provenance chains to include more preceding organisations.** The created provenance chains are scoped by the scope of the BY-COVID project. In particular, the project and related use cases were heavily focused on data (integration, processing, analysis, etc.). However, the sample acquisition and data derivation parts of the data life cycle were excluded. As a consequence, the provenance chains do not document data generation and preceding steps. For that reason, continuing prototype adoption of the provenance model by organisations like hospitals, biobanks, or analytical laboratories is vital to support full traceability in a real-life production environment.

The Workflow Run RO-Crate profiles constitute a data model to describe the provenance of a computational workflow run, as well as contextual metadata about the workflow and associated entities such as inputs and outputs. The model is flexible and allows for descriptions at different granularity levels. In particular, the Process Run Crate profile has been used to create an RO-Crate representation of the WP5 T5.2 baseline use case, as described above.

7. Conclusions

The development and adoption of the provenance model and the RO-Crate profiles carried out in the BY-COVID project was successful. In particular, the project heavily contributed to the mechanisms for capturing machine-actionable and interoperable provenance information for infectious diseases-related domains and provided a groundwork for its further development and standardisation in these domains (especially with regard to the ISO 23494 provenance standard series).

8. Next steps

The developed provenance model will be further refined and applied in various projects. Currently, there are two projects that adopt the results. 1) EvolveBBMRI funded by EU's Horizon Europe adopts the model for the development of an operational infrastructure for provenance in the BBMRI-ERIC consortium. In particular, the infrastructure will be used by European biobanks that are members of the consortium to document the evolution of respective biological samples. 2) BIOINDUSTRY 4.0 adopts the provenance model to document digital twins for bioprocesses, including links to the data used to train the twins, and the source biological material, from which the data was generated. In addition, the model is currently included in several project proposals that are being prepared by the BBMRI-ERIC.

Future plans for Workflow Run RO-Crate include the representation of resource requirements (prospective), of resource usage (retrospective) and of the execution environment. Interoperability with the GA4GH cloud APIs is also being explored. Several EOSC projects are further developing WRROC, e.g. EuroScienceGateway⁸⁹ will expand the use of RO-Crate in Galaxy to include import and publishing as FAIR Digital Objects, EOSC-EVERSE⁹⁰ will explore software quality aspects of Five Safes Crate and WRROC reproducibility with WfExS workflow execution, EOSC-ENTRUST⁹¹ will expand on the Five Safes Crates and federated analytics. Other research domains showing interest in WRROC includes climate science, biodiversity and social sciences.

9. Impact

As the adoption of the CPM in BY-COVID project led to its refinement and extension, the feedback on the model was provided to the ISO TC 276 WG5 where the development of the standardised provenance information model for biological material and data is grounded.

⁸⁹ <https://eurosciencegateway.eu/>

⁹⁰ <https://everse.software/>

⁹¹ <http://eosc-entrust.eu/>

This way, the project directly contributed to the development of a novel provenance information standard that aims to be adopted by both academia and industry globally.

The domain specific part of the resulting provenance information can be perceived as a new state-of-the-art for standardised provenance information for infectious diseases, which provides a new groundwork for future research and development in this domain.

Workflow Run RO-Crate has already been implemented in six workflow management systems: Galaxy, COMPSs, Streamflow, WfExS, Sapporo and Autosubmit, allowing their users to automatically generate RO-Crates containing workflow execution provenance information. In addition, the model has been extended to create the Five Safes RO-Crate profile, which deals with sensitive data in federated workflow runs across trusted research environments.

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11. Appendices

11.1 Appendix I: Simplification of the CPM

This section contains a specification of the new version of traversal information that is part of a provenance component generated according to the CPM (Figure 4.1.2). Table 1 contains an updated list of types and their semantics that are used to express the traversal information.

Provenance structure type	Semantics	Usage	Relation to PROV-DM
<code>backwardConnector</code>	<p>A PROV entity that represents a snapshot of the exchanged object at the time of its exposure by a sender.</p> <p>In the resulting provenance information, the entity represents an external input for the process documented by a particular provenance component. External input is an input which is an output of a process documented by a provenance component which can be linked to to form a provenance chain.</p>	<p>The <code>backwardConnector</code> type is present in the receiver's provenance information, and contains links to metadata about the previous component of the chain. Identifier of the <code>backwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>forwardConnector</code> (having the prefix of the sender).</p>	<p>The <code>backwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code>, written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:backwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.</p>
<code>forwardConnector</code>	<p>A PROV entity that represents a snapshot of the exchanged object at the time of its exposure by a sender.</p> <p>In the resulting provenance information, the entity represents an exposed output of the process documented by the provenance component.</p>	<p>The <code>forwardConnector</code> type is present in the sender's provenance information, and contains links to metadata about the consecutive component of the chain. Identifier of the <code>forwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective</p>	<p>The <code>forwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code>, written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:forwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.</p>

	Exposed output is an output which can be consequently used by other processes which are to be documented by a provenance component and linked to the current component to form a provenance chain.	<code>backwardConnector</code> (having the prefix of the sender).	
<code>mainActivity</code>	A PROV activity that represents how input of the current process (<code>currentConnector</code>) became an output of the current process (<code>forwardConnector</code>).	The <code>mainActivity</code> contains links to metadata about the provenance components in which the activity is present.	The <code>mainActivity</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:activity</code> , written as <code>activity(id, [prov:type='cpm:mainActivity'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>senderAgent</code>	A PROV agent that represents responsibility for the preceding step in the chain.		The <code>senderAgent</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:agent</code> , written as <code>agent(id, [prov:type='cpm:senderAgent'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>jumpForwardConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents an output of a process, whose derivatives are used in a non-adjacent consecutive step.	The <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> type is present in the sender's provenance information, and contains information about one of the consecutive but "non-adjacent" components of the chain. Identifier of the corresponding <code>jumpBackwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> .	The <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:jumpForwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.

jumpBackwardConnector	A PROV entity that represents an object from which an input of the described process was derived, and which is coming from a non-adjacent previous step.	The jumpBackwardConnector type is present in the receiver's provenance information, and contains information about one of the preceding but "non-adjacent" components of the chain. Identifier of the corresponding jumpForwardConnector is the same as the identifier of the respective jumpBackwardConnector.	The jumpBackwardConnector is a specialisation of prov:entity, written as entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:jumpBackwardConnector']) in PROV-N notation.
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Table 1: An updated list of the CPM types which form the basis of traversal information and provenance backbone of a provenance chain. The original list of the types was presented in the EOSC-Life project deliverable⁹².

The traversal information is represented in provenance information as a provenance graph with prescribed structure. The simplified structure is depicted in Figure 11.1.1. The structure of the backbone is the following:

- The mainActivity activity uses (prov:used) the backwardConnector entities and generates (prov:wasGeneratedBy) forwardConnector entities. Each pair of backwardConnector and respective forwardConnector is related using derivation (prov:wasDerivedFrom) relation if and only if the particular forwardConnector was somehow affected by the currentConnector.
- backwardConnector entity is attributed (prov:wasAttributedTo) to senderAgent.

Figure 11.1.1 Provenance graph structure of the traversal information. The structure is the result of simplification of the original structure.

⁹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279525>

11.2. Appendix II: Provenance Chains Operations

Minimal content of a provenance chain component

Each component of a provenance chain must contain at least two types of provenance structures as part of the traversal information: the main activity and the forward connector (Figure 11.2.1).

Figure 11.2.1 Minimal content of a provenance component.

The forward connector serves to connect additional provenance components without any modification of the existing component. In particular, if a documented object is passed from a sender to a receiver, the sender also passes the identifier of the component and the identifier of the forward connector. The receiver then can include these two identifiers in his provenance component, which essentially creates a backward link from the receiver's component to the sender's one.

A provenance component without a backward connector is always considered as the beginning of a provenance chain, and each provenance chain must contain at least one such component. Each provenance chain must be built up from such a provenance component.

Adding a consecutive provenance component

This section describes the procedure which adds a successive provenance component.

Step 1: Consider an existing provenance component. Without loss of generality, the component may be the start of a provenance chain. The important part of the component is the forward connector, which will be used to connect the consecutive provenance component.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. As the forward connector does not link to any consecutive bundle yet, the corresponding entry does not contain respective information.

main_A resolves to:

main_A	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_A_v1	meta_bundle_A
con_A resolves to:			
con_A	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-

Step 2: The output of the main activity is passed to the receiver together with the identifier of the existing provenance component and the forward connector identifier that represents the output. Consecutively, the receiver can finalise his provenance component. Inclusion of the connector in the finalised component essentially creates a backward link from the receiver's component to the sender's one.

This way, multiple consecutive components can be added to the chain. For instance, the connector may represent a dataset which is used by multiple organisations, so each of the organisations can use the proposed mechanism to link their provenance component. However, the current state of the chain provides support only for the backward traversal of the chain, meaning that there is no link from the sender to the receiver yet.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. The table can now be used to traverse the chain in the backward direction from the bundle_B_v1:

1. Resolve the backward connector ID (con_A).
2. Find the corresponding entity in the entries using the backwardConnector type (con_A).
3. Retrieve the linked meta-bundle identifier (meta_bundle_A) and resolve it to get to the content.
4. Check whether the referenced bundle (bundle_A_v1) has a newer version and decide which of the versions should be used. At this point, only a single version of the bundle exists.

Adding multiple consecutive provenance components to the chain in a way that all of them will be linked to the bundle_A_v1 will not disrupt the traversal algorithm, as all of them will link to the same sender's bundle. However, this is based on the presumption that a connector ID is used in a single bundle. Without this presumption, it would be not clear which bundle should be followed in the traversal.

main_A resolves to:			
main_A	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_A_v1	meta_bundle_A

main_B resolves to:			
main_B	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_B_v1	meta_bundle_B
con_A resolves to:			
con_A	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_A	cpm:backwardConnector	bundle_A_v1	meta_bundle_A
con_B resolves to:			
con_B	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-

Step 3 (optional): Pingback to the sender. The sender is notified about the existence of a new linked provenance component, and is provided with the component identifier (and possibly its meta-provenance). As the initial component can not be modified directly, its new version with the forward link is created (versions are expressed in meta-provenance).

The receiver component identifier and its meta-provenance identifier must be associated, so multiple forward links can be created using a single connector (not presented).

As a consequence, in order to traverse the chain in the forward direction the latest version of a component must be used. The proposed mechanism also works in scenarios where the bundle_a_v1 is not the beginning of the chain.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. The table can now be used to traverse the chain in both the forward and backward directions.

main_A resolves to:			
main_A	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_A_v1	meta_bundle_A
main_A	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_A_v2	meta_bundle_A
main_B resolves to:			
main_B	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_B_v1	meta_bundle_B

con_A resolves to:			
con_A	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_A	cpm:backwardConnector	bundle_A_v1	meta_bundle_A
con_A	cpm:forwardConnector	bundle_B_v1	meta_bundle_B
con_B resolves to:			
con_B	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-

For traversing the chain in the backward direction from the bundle_B_v1:

1. Resolve the backward connector ID (con_A).
2. Find the corresponding entity in the entries using the backwardConnector type (con_A).
3. Retrieve the linked meta-bundle identifier (meta_bundle_A) and resolve it to get to the content.
4. Check whether the referenced bundle (bundle_A_v1) has a newer version and decide which of the versions should be used. At this point, the reference bundle has two versions (bundle_A_v1, bundle_A_v2) and from the meta-bundle can be seen that the referenced bundle has been obsoleted by a newer version.

For traversing the chain in the forward direction from the bundle_A_v2:

1. Resolve the forward connector ID (con_A).
2. Find the corresponding entity in the entries using the forwardConnector type (con_A).
3. Retrieve the linked meta-bundle identifier (meta_bundle_B) and resolve it to get to the content.
4. Check whether the referenced bundle (bundle_B_v1) has a newer version and decide which of the versions should be used. At this point, the reference bundle has only a single version.

Adding multiple consecutive provenance components to the chain in a way that all of them will be linked to various versions of the bundle_A_v1 will not disrupt the traversal algorithm presuming that the traversal algorithm can decide which version of the bundle should be used. In addition, we presume that a connector ID is used only in multiple versions of a single bundle, not multiple bundles. Enabling the presence of a connector in multiple bundles (unrelated with versions) would then require that the traversal algorithm can decide which bundle should be used.

Adding a preceding provenance component

This section describes the procedure which adds a preceding provenance component. This might happen especially in legacy use cases for which provenance chains are constructed

retrospectively. In such scenarios, the order of generating/finalising provenance components does not necessarily follow their order in the resulting chain.

Step 1: Consider an existing provenance component. By presumption, there is no backward connector in the existing component.

At this stage, the existing component does not document any external inputs of the main activity. However, presume that an external input exists, because otherwise adding a preceding component would not make sense.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. As the forward connector does not link to any consecutive bundle yet, the corresponding entry does not contain respective information.

main_D resolves to:			
main_D	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_D_v1	meta_bundle_D
con_D resolves to:			
con_D	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-

Step 2: Finalise a provenance component with an exposed output that corresponds to the external input of the existing component. At this point, there are two independent provenance components.

At this point, the independent provenance components shall be linked. This is only possible when one of the responsible subjects – either sender or receiver – initiates the linkage⁹³, otherwise the components will stay independent.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. As the forward connectors do not link to any consecutive bundle yet, the corresponding entries do not contain respective information.

main_D resolves to:			
main_D	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_D_v1	meta_bundle_D
main_C resolves to:			
main_C	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_C_v1	meta_bundle_C
con_D resolves to:			
con_D	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_C resolves to:			
con_C	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-

Step 3: Linking the bundles together. With no respect to who initiates the linkage, the identifier of the forward connector must be passed from the sender to the receiver to enable backward navigation. As the receiver can not update the existing component directly, a new version of the bundle must be created.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. The table can now be used to traverse the chain in the backward direction from the bundle_D_v2

⁹³ Different initiators may better fit different scenarios. For instance, when a public dataset is openly provided and used, the provider does not necessarily know who the receivers are. In such a scenario, it may be more appropriate that the receivers initiate the linkage. On the other hand, when a biobank provides samples to organisations, the biobank typically tracks the receivers of the samples. In such a scenario, the biobank may notify all potential receivers who received a sample.

using the same algorithm as in the step 2 of the *Adding a consecutive provenance component*.

main_D resolves to:			
main_D	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_D_v1	meta_bundle_D
main_C resolves to:			
main_C	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_C_v1	meta_bundle_C
con_D resolves to:			
con_D	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_C resolves to:			
con_C	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_C	cpm:backwardConnector	bundle_C_v1	meta_bundle_C

Step 4 (optional): The sender can be notified about the finalisation of the receiver's bundle to enable forward navigation. As the sender can not update the existing component directly, a new version of the bundle must be created.

The following table lists the entries to which the persistent identifiers resolve to. The table can now be used to traverse the chain in the forward direction from the bundle_C_v2.

main_D resolves to:			
main_D	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_D_v1	meta_bundle_D
main_C resolves to:			
main_C	cpm:mainActivity	bundle_C_v1	meta_bundle_C
con_D resolves to:			

con_D	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_C resolves to:			
con_C	cpm:forwardConnector	-	-
con_C	cpm:backwardConnector	bundle_C_v1	meta_bundle_C
con_C	cpm:forwardConnector	bundle_D_v2	meta_bundle_D

11.3 Appendix III: BY COVID GA 2023 Provenance Workshop Template

Respondents: <first name, last name, email>;

What is the name of the described process?

Name the process using a single phrase, e.g., data generation, data processing, AI model training, AI model evaluation, biological samples collection, etc.

What is the described process about?

Describe the described process and its scope, e.g., : What domain is the described process from? What is the goal of the described process? Are there preceding/successive processes? Is the described process part of a use case in WP5?

What are the inputs of the described process?

List the inputs of the described process and for each of them, provide a brief description.

What quality measures do you apply to the above inputs?

List the quality control measures applied to each of the inputs listed above and for each of them, provide a brief description.

What are outputs of the described process?

List the outputs of the described process and for each of them, provide a brief description.

What quality measures do you apply to the above outputs?

List the quality control measures applied to each of the outputs listed above and for each of them, provide a brief description.

Does the described process consist of any sub-processes?

The described process may consist of multiple sub-processes/stages, which can be described individually. The sub-processes can be run sequentially (one after another) or in parallel. If this is the case for the described process, list the sub-processes, and provide a brief description for all of them.

Who is responsible for the documented process and the sub-processes?

Describe responsibilities related to the documented process, sub-processes, or the final/intermediate results.

What are the intermediate or subsidiary results of the described process?

The described process may generate objects that are not considered as the final results of it. This may include datasets in intermediate states, log files, or biological waste. These objects can be generated or consumed by sub-processes. If this is the case for the described process, list these intermediate or subsidiary results, and provide a brief description for all of them.

What quality checks are implemented in the subprocesses or applied to the intermediate results?

List and briefly describe the quality measures taken in each of the sub-processes listed above and the quality control measures applied to the intermediate or subsidiary results.

What kind of identifiers are used to identify the objects related to the described process?

For each of the inputs, outputs, intermediate/subsidiary results, or responsibilities, describe the identifiers used to identify the object. For instance:

Is the identifier globally unique?

Can the identifier be reassigned to another object?

Is the identifier generated “internally” (e.g., by a system that stores related data) or “externally” (e.g., by an external service or organisation)?

Does the identifier belong to a scheme (URI/URL, DOI, ORCID, ...)?

Is there any information that should be documented about the described process and which must stay confidential?

Some parts of provenance information may be confidential or sensitive. This includes not only personal information about responsible people or patients/donors, but also, for instance, information about transportation of pathogens.

Is the information provided in this template somehow documented for the described process? If yes, how?

11.4 Appendix IV: Provenance Chains for Infectious Diseases

The CPM provenance model is intended for the documentation of objects (and its derivatives) that are exchanged between organisations. For instance, a biological sample can be acquired in a hospital, the sample can be then transferred to a laboratory where it is used as a source for data generation (e.g., omics or image data), and the resulting data can be further provided to a computer science research group for further processing and analysis. In such a scenario, each organisation/group involved can document only a portion of the object's life cycle. According to the CPM, each organisation creates a provenance component that contains relevant information and links it to a component documenting the preceding/consecutive step. As a result, the provenance components form a provenance chain. This is depicted in Figure 11.4.1.

Figure 11.4.1. Simplified schema of a provenance chain created according to the CPM (ISO 23494-2).

This appendix demonstrates the usage of the CPM to document various use cases related to Infectious Diseases. The provenance chains presented in this deliverable are created for use cases that are part of the project. The components of provenance chains are depicted using diagrams that loosely follow the conventions for provenance diagrams defined in W3C PROV⁹⁴.

Depending on the maturity of each use case, the provenance diagrams represent either 1) resulting provenance information documenting an actual execution of a particular process, or 2) a provenance template, which can be instantiated when the process is executed.

Provenance components were created for the following use cases:

1. Use Case 1: COVID-19 Raw Read Dataset Deposition
2. Use Case 2: WP2 – Clinical health data conversion into the OMOP Common Data Model

⁹⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-primer-20130430/>

3. Use Case 3: WP5 – Baseline use case – Standardised workflow for population health research (use case on "SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine(s) effectiveness in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection")
4. Use Case 4: WP5 - Clinical trials data sharing use case

Use Case 1: COVID-19 Raw Read Dataset Deposition

The use case is about raw read data sharing at an open data repository. These open data repositories are underlying the data hubs at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) which support data submissions related to biological samples that are generated by data generators/providers. Through data submission at the ENA, it enables further metadata-level presentation by specific portals. In this case, the CPM is used to document a COVID-19 raw read dataset, which also shows in the COVID-19 Data Portal⁹⁵.

The inputs of the process are dependent on the type of sequencing experiment. In this particular case, the inputs are raw read dataset provided in a .fq format, that is automatically converted into other standardised formats (BAM/FASTQ). In addition, users provide various metadata related to a particular dataset. The result of the process is a deposited dataset consisting of multiple files.

The resulting provenance component is depicted in Figure 11.4.2.

The provenance backbone part of the resulting provenance component contains a single `forwardConnector` entity, as there is only a single exposed output of the process: the archived dataset. If provenance information about the raw input dataset was generated according to the CPM, there would be a single `backwardConnector` referring to corresponding provenance component which would represent the input dataset generation or processing that preceded the deposition.

The domain specific part of the resulting provenance component contains provenance structures that represent the deposition process: 1) information about the data generation part, as these are present as meta-data in the archive; 2) submission of the input data set into the archive; 3) automated generation of the dataset in the standardised format.

⁹⁵ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search?query=ERR11837803&requestFrom=searchBox>

Figure 11.4.2. A provenance component documenting the COVID-19 Raw Read Dataset deposition into a data hub.

Use Case 2: Clinical health data conversion into the OMOP Common Data Model

The goal of the use case – health data conversion – is to transform an existing dataset containing research or clinical health data into the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM). The dataset can be in any database format, alongside a data dictionary that explains the meaning of each entry, and any existing recognised vocabularies used to codify entries. There are several inputs for the conversion, for instance: the input dataset, consisting of a set of tables in CSV format; Optional Data dictionary in CSV format; the original and transformed values of all previously mapped datasets processed by the same system; configuration files; and various SW tools. The results of the conversion are: a set of TSV files containing the transformed dataset in OMOP format - one file per OMOP table; the JSON mapping rules; a log file containing information about the transformation process, including success statistics and any dropped records.

The resulting provenance component is depicted in Figure 11.4.3.

The provenance backbone part of the provenance component contains a single `forwardConnector` entity, as there is only a single exposed output of the process: the transformed dataset. If provenance information about the raw input dataset was generated according to the CPM, there would be a `backwardConnector` referring to the corresponding provenance component, which would represent the input dataset generation or processing that preceded the conversion. In addition, as the transformation can exploit the information about the past transformations carried out by the system, additional `backwardConnectors` can refer to provenance components that document already transformed datasets.

The domain specific part of the provenance component represents information about the subprocesses of the conversion and about the intermediate results: scan report file is used as a result of the input dataset profiling. The report is then uploaded to the system, where it is used by rules generation activity that also uses the input data dictionary, and possibly existing datasets that are already transformed and present in the system. The generated mapping rules are then augmented by the rules augmentation activity, and these are then downloaded from the system to be applied to the input dataset. The application of the rules generates the resulting dataset in the OMOP CDM.

Figure 11.4.3 A provenance component documenting clinical health data conversion into the OMOP CDM.

Use Case 3: Baseline use case – Standardised workflow for population health research

The BY-COVID Baseline Use Case prototyped a workflow standard for population health research. The workflow provides a structured process for performing causal inference based on real-world observational data from different sources in multiple regions or countries to respond to policy-relevant questions. The proposed workflow consists of several steps, each of which can be executed by a different organisation:

1. Conceptual and instrumental phase of developing an analytical pipeline for a specific policy-relevant question. This step is realised by a *coordination node*.
2. Distributed extraction, linkage, and transformation procedures of the source data from different sources into a standardised representation suitable for answering the research question and deploying the pipeline (as specified in a Common Data Model). This step is performed by a *participating node*.
3. Distribution of the pipeline from the coordination node to participating nodes, its distributed deployment and execution upon the linked and transformed data, and providing the aggregated non-sensitive results to the coordination node.
4. Analysis of the results from participating nodes by the coordination node.

There are several provenance components created for this use case. Each provenance component documents a different step of the workflow carried out by a particular organisation. In addition, depending on the maturity of each step, the resulting provenance components contain different levels of information. As a result, the following provenance components were created:

1. Step 1 of the workflow: Analytical pipeline development by coordination node – Sciensano, Belgium & IACS, Spain.
2. Step 2 of the workflow: Data transformation step – Sciensano, Belgium
3. Step 2 of the workflow: Data transformation step – Aragon, Spain
4. Step 3 of the workflow: Pipeline execution – Brussels and Wallonia, Belgium
5. Step 3 of the workflow: Pipeline execution – Aragon, Spain
6. Step 4 of the workflow: Meta-analysis of the results.

The resulting provenance chain for the Baseline use case is depicted in Figure 11.4.4. The domain specific provenance part of the resulting provenance components is simplified in a way that the `wasDerivedFrom` relation is sometimes omitted for better readability of the diagrams.

Figure 11.4.4 Provenance chain for the Baseline use case.

Step 1: Analytical pipeline development, Sciensano (Belgium) & IACS (Spain)

The first step of the pipeline carried out by a coordination node – Sciensano, Belgium & IACS (Spain) – consists of defining a research question, establishing a causal model, identifying and specifying data requirements in a common data model (CDM), generating synthetic data, and developing an interoperable and reproducible analytical pipeline. The research question for the baseline use case is "*How effective have the SARS-CoV-2 vaccination programmes been in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infections?*".

The resulting provenance component is depicted in Figure 11.4.5.

The provenance backbone part of the provenance component contains two `forwardConnector` entities, as there are two exposed outputs of the process: 1) implementation of the analytical pipeline, and 2) Common Data Model (CDM) specification, according to which the source data will be later transformed by participating nodes.

The domain specific part represents information about the intermediate results of the pipeline development: research question, a causal model to represent the question, CDM specifying requirements on the input data for the pipeline, synthetic data used for the pipeline development, and the pipeline itself.

Figure 11.4.5 A provenance component documenting the preparation of the analytical pipeline performed by the coordination node – Sciensano.

Step 2: Data Transformation Step, Sciensano (Belgium) and IACS (Spain)

The data transformation step includes acquiring data from source databases, and their transformation according to the requirements defined in the CDM.

The resulting provenance component for Sciensano (Belgium) is depicted in Figure 11.4.6. The diagram presented contains placeholders for missing values, as the results of this step have not been published yet. The provenance backbone part of the resulting provenance contains a single `backwardConnector` entity representing the CDM specification from step 1, and a single `forwardConnector` entity representing the transformed dataset. The domain specific part represents information about the intermediate results of the transformation: entities that represent source databases, data extracted from the databases, intermediate results of the data integration, and the resulting transformed dataset.

The resulting provenance component for IACS (Spain) is depicted in Figure 11.4.7. It follows the same graph structure as the diagram for Belgium execution of the step 2, it should just contain links to different external sources (e.g., a different Secure Processing Environment ID or different links to the source databases).

Figure 11.4.6 A provenance component documenting the transformation of the input data for the analytical pipeline performed by a participating node – Sciensano.

Step 3: Pipeline Execution Step, Sciensano (Belgium) and IACS (Spain)

The pipeline execution step consists of a single task – deployment and execution of the pipeline on the transformed data.

The resulting provenance component for Sciensano (Belgium) is depicted in Figure 11.4.8. The diagram presented contains placeholders for missing values, as the results of this step have not been published yet. The provenance backbone part of the resulting provenance component contains two `backwardConnector` entities – the pipeline from step 1 and the Belgium dataset from step 2. The backbone contains a single `forwardConnector`, as there is a single exposed output of this step – the interactive report containing results of the execution and a `xlsx` file used for comparative/meta-analysis. The domain specific part represents information about the intermediate and side results of the pipeline execution.

The resulting provenance component for IACS (Spain) is depicted in Figure 11.4.9. It follows the same graph structure as the diagram for Belgium execution of the step 3, it should just contain links to different external sources (e.g., a different DOI of the interactive report).

Figure 11.4.8 A provenance component documenting the execution of the analytical pipeline performed by a participating node – Sciensano.

Figure 11.4.9 A provenance component documenting the execution of the analytical pipeline performed by a participating node – IACS.

The resulting provenance component is depicted in Figure 11.4.11. The diagram presented contains placeholders for missing values, as the EU-COVAT-1-AGED dataset is still being collected, so it has not been shared within the repository yet.

The provenance backbone part of the resulting provenance component contains a single `forwardConnector` entity, as there is only a single exposed output of the process: the advertised dataset. If provenance information about the raw input dataset was generated according to the CPM, there would be a `backwardConnector` referring to corresponding provenance component, which would represent the input dataset generation or processing that preceded the conversion.

The domain specific part of the resulting provenance component represents information about the subprocesses of the sharing and about the intermediate results: first, the input digital objects are uploaded to the system, and then are advertised after a quality check.

